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IMPACT OF PARENTS TEACHER MEETING ON THE PERFORMANCE OF PERSPECTIVE TEACHERS

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Abstract

The present study aims at finding whether there is significant impact of parents teacher meeting on the performance of perspective teachers. For this purpose a sample of 195 pupil teachers was selected randomly from Sant Baba Bhag Singh Institute of Education Jalandhar. The marks obtained in the house test were taken indicators of academic performance. The impact of successive parents teacher meeting were compared with the results of final tests. Analysis of results suggests the marks of final tests were significantly higher than house tests.

The performance of students depends upon multiple reasons. The particular interests, aptitudes and various psycho-socio factors influence the academic performance of students. Disregarding the age of students it is felt that certain social factors do sway the performance of students. The association of parents and teachers can profusely contribute in the higher performance of students. In other way the school may affect home environments in positive ways with its intentional, consistent interaction with parents.

The interrelation of home and school is quite considerable. Both of them are indispensable. They cannot survive in aloof. Their interdependence on each other is all absorbing. In fact if both of them learn the significant reliance of their relationship then only they could effectively contribute in teaching learning process. Sam Janis et.al .(2004) have adopted following strategies to study the school level effects of parent engagement in the achievement of the students:

- Parent participation in decision making at school
- Explicit discussions of the role of parents, teachers and students around compacts, learning standards and homework policies
- Reading school- home links aligned with state standards and in-class instruction
- Parent education focused on home reading and study habits
- Outreach through home visits, family nights and a family resource library

School can provide parent education based on the role of parents in helping their children meet state learning standards. An ongoing conversation between parents and teachers about the role of each children's learning is key to building the relationship and understanding that enhances school

performance. It is a matter of concern that the performance of pupil teachers could be improved if they are given tests .

From the limited evidence available, Henderson and Mapp (2002) draw convincing conclusions as to the qualities that successful school's efforts to engage families might include . These qualities (such as building a foundation of trust strategies to learning objectives and teaching out to engage parents beyond the school) are found in school where parents involvement is measurably high in specific programmes that demonstrate effects on learning outcomes and in schools that exhibit levels of achievements . Henderson and Mapp (2002) echo Swaps (1993) conclusions that effect parents engagements must be comprehensive in nature with the school consistently interfaces with parents at many points in many venues over the course of the schooling years . The school may affect home environment in positive ways with its intentional consist interaction with parents.

Sam Janis et.al . (2004) describe with the help of following figure this demonstrate the students' family and school variables that impinge upon student learning outcomes both individual and whole. This is a dynamic system subject to influence at every point. It can be influenced by focused and intentional intervention by the school itself through the relationship expectations and opportunities for association it creates within the community of those intimately attached to it "School community relationship among students, family and school personal " as designated in a box as the right figure is the vehicle through which the school , through its policies and practices can exert influence on family behaviour linked to school learning . That the same box also holds the reservoir of human and social capital that may be turned to influencing and improving the school itself. Thus the connection between schooling and the community in the figure is one that pressures in the both directions. The study concluded that solid foundation proved that a critical mass of constructive, school home activity can be generated in schools can be generated in a relatively short period of time in schools most in need of programming to engage parents in children's learning. The comprehensive nature of the intervention was itself the source of impact of learning rather than the individual paths. As the teacher enlist the support of parents in learning in different ways at different points in time, they are reminded of the advantages of such alliance and the child learning increasingly becomes the focus of their interactions with parents.

Relationship among student family and school variables and their effects on student learning outcomes.

The above flowchart shows the significant interdependence of various variables like school, students and their families. The learning of a student is prominently effected by the interactions between school and family.

Specifically, schools can clearly articulate their expectations of parents and regularly communicate with parents about what children are learning, suggesting what parents can do to help. School-home compacts, reading school-home links, and explicit homework policies are examples of communication about expectations and support for children's learning. Schools can also provide opportunities for parents to talk with school personnel about parents' role in their children's education through home visits, family nights, and well-planned parent-teacher conferences and open houses. Schools can provide parent education based on the role of parents in helping their children meet state learning standards. An ongoing conversation between parents and teachers about the role of each in children's learning is key to building the relationship and understanding that enhances school performance.

According to Blatchford et.al. (Dec.2011)it is widely recognized that we need to know more about effects of class size on classroom interactions and pupil behavior. This paper extends research by comparing effects on pupil classroom engagement and teacher-pupil interaction, and examining if effects vary by pupil attainment level and between primary and secondary schools. Systematic observations were carried out on 686 pupils in 49 schools. Multilevel regression methods were used to examine relationships between class size and observation measures, controlling for potentially confounding factors like pupil attainment. At primary and secondary levels smaller classes led to pupils receiving more individual attention from teachers, and having more active interactions with them. Classroom engagement decreased in larger classes, but, contrary to expectation, this was particularly marked for lower attaining pupils at secondary level. Low attaining pupils can therefore benefit from smaller classes at secondary level in terms of more individual attention and facilitating engagement in learning.

Adeyemi, Babatunde(2010) viewed the teacher plays a significant role in the intellectual development of the pupils, using various assessment and teaching styles to improve pupils' performance in school subjects. The study therefore investigated the effect of some teacher related factors: teacher level of awareness of assessment style, teacher assessment style, teacher personal

characteristics (qualification, year of experience and teaching styles) on pupils' achievement in Social Studies in primary schools. The study was a co relational type. Multi-stage sampling technique was employed in selecting three states from the existing six states that constitute Southwestern zone in Nigeria. Three instruments were used in the study. Three research questions emanated from the study and were analysed using mean, standard deviation, graphical illustration and multiple regression analysis. Results revealed that Social Studies teachers engaged more in formal authority and facilitation teaching styles. There was a significant relationship among teacher related factors and pupils' achievement in Social Studies. Only two predictors had significant relative effect on pupils' achievement in Social Studies. It was concluded that teaching and assessment styles of teachers are crucial in the learning of Social Studies. Workshops and seminars should therefore be organized for teachers on various teaching styles.

According to Pecek, Macura et.al(2012) in the ongoing trend towards inclusive education, initial teacher education programmes must ensure that prospective teachers are prepared to teach all pupils effectively. The study presented in this paper aimed to explore the attitudes of teacher candidates in Serbia and Slovenia towards responsibility for the teaching and learning of vulnerable pupils in mainstream elementary schools. Using a quantitative approach, the study sought to elicit teacher candidates' views about division of responsibility for the academic achievement and additional support of vulnerable pupils and their views on the factors that most affect learning difficulties in those pupils. The findings indicate that teacher candidates' feelings of responsibility are unlikely to help when instructing vulnerable pupils. The implications of these findings are discussed and we suggest several ways to improve teacher education programmes to promote inclusive education based on the concept of quality education for all.

Elstad,et.al. (2012)The purpose of this article was to explore the influence of parents and teachers on the deep learning approach of pupils by estimating the strength of the relationships between these factors and the motivation, volition and deep learning approach of Norwegian 16-year-olds. Structural equation modeling for cross-sectional survey data was used to estimate the path coefficients. A total of 1,112 students voluntarily participated. The analysis indicated that the teachers' perceived efforts to influence and stimulate the deep learning approach of the pupils had some effect. Parental efforts in this respect did not appear to have any noticeable influence on the pupils'

motivation, volition or deep learning approach. Teacher pressure was found to influence the motivation and deep learning approach, and teachers can make conscious use of this effect in order to improve the students' performance. It was concluded that for pupils who lack educational motivation, the teacher has an important function in motivating greater effort with schoolwork and stimulating a more effective deep learning approach. The current study provides new knowledge concerning the influence of teachers and parents on students' learning efforts.

Aturupane, Harsha et.al(2013) had opined that one of the eight Millennium Development Goals is that all children in developing countries should complete primary education. At the child and household level, educated parents, better nutrition, high daily attendance, enrollment in private tutoring classes, exercise books, electric lighting, and children's books at home all appear to increase learning, while hearing problems have a strong negative effect. Among school variables, principals' and teachers' years of experience, collaborating with other schools in a "school family," and meetings between parents and teachers all appear to have positive impacts on students' scores. Estimates that exclude some of the variables available in the unusually rich data yield different results, which suggests that results based on less complete data are likely to suffer from omitted variable bias. A final section provides recommendations for education policies in Sri Lanka.

Shen, Jianping et.al,(2014);The authors examined parental involvement's (PI) impact on school performance. The hierarchical linear modeling method was applied to national Schools and Staffing Survey 2007-2008 data. They found that PI variables explained significant variance for the outcomes of (a) meeting adequate yearly progress (AYP) and (b) being free from sanctions. The authors also found that PI in (a) open houses, (b) parent-teacher conferences, and (c) special events were statistically significant positive predictors for meeting AYP, and that PI (a) on hiring teachers, (b) in open houses, and (c) in special events were statistically significant positive predictors for being free from sanctions. PI on hiring teachers seemed to be an important strategy in turning around schools. The similarity and difference in the sets of statistically significant predictors for both outcomes indicate that some PI strategies were effective for all schools while others were effective for particular situations. Implications and limitations of the study were discussed.

Cho, YoonJung; Shim, Sungok Serena(2013)the present study investigated contextual and personal factors associated with teachers' achievement goals for teaching. A total of 211 teachers completed an online survey. Hierarchical multiple regression analyses revealed that perceived school mastery goal structure and performance goal structure predicted teachers' mastery goals and performance-approach goals, respectively. Teachers' sense of efficacy moderated the effect of perceived school goal structures on achievement goals for teaching. Teachers with high teaching efficacy maintained personal achievement goals for teaching even when their schools emphasized conflicting goals. However, teachers with low teaching efficacy tended to assimilate the goals promoted by their schools.

Review of related literature reveal that few studies were conducted like Social Studies teachers engaged more in formal authority and facilitation teaching styles. There was a significant relationship among teacher related factors and pupils' achievement in Social Studies. Significant and positive effects of Parental involvement (PI) on adequate yearly progress (AYP) , contextual and personal factors associated with teachers' achievement goals for teaching and research on various variables like principals' and teachers' years of experience, collaborating with other schools in a "school family," ; were areas of research by several researchers. Several ways to improve teacher education programmes to promote inclusive education based on the concept of quality education for all were also focus of investigation.

But no research is conducted on pupil teachers and the impacts of parents' teacher meeting on them. Henceforth the investigator decided to see the impact of parents teacher meeting on the performance of pupil teachers.

OBJECTIVES

- To find out the impact of parents teacher meeting on the academic performance of the students of B.Ed course.
- To find out the effects and outcomes of parents teacher meeting on students' performance by comparing the results of house test and final results.

To see the impact of Parents Teacher on the academic performance of students of B .Ed. the data of two consecutive years had been collected i.e. 2012 and 2013. The marks were the indicators to test the performance of students of B.Ed course. The marks of house tests of both years were collected and compared with the final results of those particular sessions. The N was 195(97 and 98) for the respective years .

HYPOTHESIS

“ There is no significant difference in the performance of perspective teachers through parents teacher meeting.”

ANALYSIS AND INTERPETATION

The data collected were analysed statistically. To study the impact of parents teacher meeting on the performance of pupil teachers the marks of house test were compared with the final marks. The house tests were followed by parents teacher meeting and strong feedback mechanism by teachers. To study the difference between the marks of house test and final test Mean, Median, Standard deviation were calculated. The difference between means were tested with the help of “t” tests. The significant differences were interpreted and results were drawn.

Interpretation Table I -Session 2012-2013

	House test	Final test
Mean	262.659	410.893
Median	267.5	408
S.D	44.851	36.883
Calculated t value	2.467	

A glance of table I depicts that the mean score of final test(410.893) is higher than mean score of house test(262.659).The value of calculated t is 2.467 and df is 186. Tabulated value of t at 0.05 level and 0.01 level of significance is 1.97 and 2.60 respectively. Table value of t at 0.05 level of confidence is less than the calculated value .It clearly indicates that parents teacher meeting has improved the marks of final test. The .So the hypothesis “There is no significant difference in the performance of perspective teachers through parents teacher meeting.” is rejected.

Table II- session 2013-2014

	House test	Final result
Mean	243.494	406.333
Median	237	403
S.D	57.697	36.942
Calculated t value	2.570	

A glance of table I depicts that the mean score of final test(406.333) is higher than mean score of house test (243.494).The value of calculated t is 2.570 and df is 186. Tabulated value of t at 0.05 level 0.01 level of significance is 1.97 and 2.60 respectively. Table value of “t” at 0.05 level of confidence is less than the calculated value . It clearly implies that the final test have improved results . So the hypothesis, “There is no significance difference in the performance of perspective teachers through parents teacher meeting. ” is rejected.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The study employed descriptive survey method. The results of house tests and final tests of two consecutive sessions of B.Ed students were compared after parents teacher meetings.The results revealed that the marks of final tests were significantly higher than house tests. The results have been discussed in the light previous findings of

Pecek, Macura et.al(2012) about teacher education program and comprehensive role of teachers instudents performance and Shen, Jianping et.al,(2014); have examined parental involvement's (PI) impact on adequate yearly progress of students. The significant impact of

Regular parents teacher meeting on the performance of students of B.Ed. is quite noteworthy and appreciable. It may be because of the strong feedback mechanism given by teacher educators and active participation of parents in the improvement of the performance of their wards for final test.

CONCLUSIONS

The following various conclusion can be drawn from the present study:

- The parental involvement play a significant role in the academic performance of students disregarding their age and class.
- The Active teacher participation in students' activities as well as his various problems can strengthened teacher- student bond.
- Regular parents teacher meetings and interactions could solve numerous behavioural, educational and psycho-social problems of students.
- The pupil teachers could be motivated to fathom the gap between them and their students by themselves getting involved in active parents teacher meeting and other activities.

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